

POLYMER-PHYSICAL ANALYSIS OF UNUSUAL MORPHOLOGICAL EFFECTS IN NATURAL FIBRE COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Natural fiber composites represent an interesting and sustainable alternative to conventional polymeric composites in both “hard” and “soft” materials applications. In a recent study unusual phenomena were found at the interface between natural fibers (e.g. flax, wool, hemp) and a biobased liquid molding resin (soyoil). These phenomena include spike and bubble shaped features (voids) triggering the breathability of the composite materials produced (eco-leather). The present study addresses intrinsic material characteristics affecting void formation (volatile induced voids). Parameter studies and comprehensive morphological and thermo-analytical investigations revealed that intrinsic material characteristics are most likely not the reason for voids, although there is a significant portion of volatiles evaporating both, from resin and fibres. However, complex interactions between resin and fibres were ascertained. Moreover compaction characteristics of the fibres are highly nonlinear. Hence, complex interactions affect morphology and have to be considered in order to tailor breathability and other selective transport characteristics of eco-leather.

1 INTRODUCTION AND MOTIVATION

Eco-leather - a highly innovative natural fiber composite - represents an interesting and sustainable alternative to natural and synthetic leather [1-4]. The product is made by mixing flax, wool, hemp or cotton fibers with bio-based liquid molding resins, for example based on soyoil. Eco-leather exhibits a substantially lower toxicity compared to natural leather and synthetic leather materials (polyurethane and PVC). Moreover, material characteristics are outstanding. Mechanical properties can be tailored easily by varying fibre, resin, and lamination and are comparable to natural leather. Interestingly eco-leather is also breathable. In order to investigate the origin of breathability in eco-leather, comprehensive morphological investigations were carried out. Representative microscopic images are shown in Fig. 1. Spike and bubble shaped features, located mainly around the natural fibres were observed. It is assumed that gas diffusion occurs by percolation along the natural fibre-feature interfaces, thus yielding breathability [5]. However, origin of bubble and spike shaped features (voids)

is not clear yet. Hence, the overall objective of our study is to investigate formation of these characteristic features in eco-leather. The findings should serve to control feature quantity, size, and shape and hence to tailor breathability and other related properties of the novel material.

Figure 1: Spike (left) and bubble-shaped (right) features detected in different eco-leather samples.

2 SOURCES OF VOIDS IN AMORPHOUS POLYMERIC MATERIALS

Depending on the application, voids can be desirable or undesirable microstructural features within a material [6]. Due to their detrimental effect on mechanical properties, voids are not desired in structural composite parts. However, voids can trigger selective transport characteristics if percolation is assured. Hence, in terms of functional properties (e.g. breathability in eco-leather) and smart materials voids may be explicitly desired. In general, there are three possible origins of voids in polymeric materials:

- volatiles,
- internal and external stress factors, or
- mechanical entrapment.

Volatile initiated voids are attributable to dissolved volatiles and moisture, which evaporate or accumulate within the composite during processing. Hence, such voids are mainly material related. Stress initiated voids are attributable either to restraint of shrinkage or to stresses generated by entrapped volatiles. Hence, such voids are affected either by material characteristics or by processing parameters. Mechanical entrapment occurs when pockets of air get trapped, for example during layup. Thus, such voids are mainly processing related. So far, eco-leather is produced by impregnating a natural fiber cloth with liquid molding resin. As a consequence, mechanical entrapment can most likely be excluded as source for voids in eco-leather [6].

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Materials and preparation of eco-leather samples

The liquid molding resin applied within the present study was based on acrylated epoxidized soya bean oil (AESO; Ebecryl 860 supplied by Allnex, Drogenbos, BE) and methacrylated lauric acid (MLAU; MFA MC818 supplied by Dixie Chemical Company, Texas, USA). A 50/50 m% composition of AESO and MLAU was mixed with 1.5m% initiator tert-Butyl peroxybenzoate (Luperox P supplied by Sigma Aldrich, Missouri, USA). The mixture was purged by using nitrogen and subsequently degassed in vacuum.

The natural fiber used for the investigations presented herein was a green felt (20% wool felt supplied by Jo-Ann Fabric and Craft Stores, Ohio, USA), consisting of 20% wool and 80% rayon.

The eco-leather is a composite made from green felt and the AESO/MLAU liquid molding resin. PVF films were used to provide a layer between the composite and the reusable mold. First the green felt was placed on a PVF film. Afterwards resin was poured on the fabric uniformly. The amount of

resin to fabric was varied systematically. 2, 2.5, 3, 4.5 and 6 parts of weight resin to fibre were investigated. Afterwards the sample was covered and tightly packed in PVF film, placed in a mould, and covered by a lid. The mould was placed in the hot press and a two-step curing process was applied: a 120 min cure step at 90°C followed by a 120 min cure step at 120°C. The applied pressure was 55psi.

3.2 Analysis of morphology

Fiber morphology was studied applying Scanning Electron Microscopy on a EOScan Tescan VEGA XL H. Prior to measurement the sample was glued on a metallic sample holder und sputtered with gold film. Eco-leather morphology was investigated on a Nikon UDM Eclipse LV1000 Optical Microscope. Micrographs were recorded on both sample surfaces. No specific sample preparation was applied.

3.3 Thermal and thermo-mechanical analysis

In order to analyse material intrinsic aspects concerning void formation in eco-leather, systematic thermo-analytical investigations were done.

Comprehensive curing studies were performed applying Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC). Pure resin as well as impregnated fibres were investigated. Resin mass was 10 ± 1 mg. Moreover thermal characteristics of the pure fibres were analysed. Fiber mass was 5 ± 0.5 mg. Thermograms were recorded under both floating air and floating nitrogen (50ml/min) on a Mettler Toledo DSC1 (Schwerzenbach, CH) in a temperature range between 20 and 200°C applying a heating rate of 10°C/min. The presented data were averaged over two measurements.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of resin and fibre was performed on a Mettler Toledo TGA/DSC (Schwerzenbach, CH) under air atmosphere. On the one hand thermograms were recorded at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. On the other hand change in sample mass during the two-step curing cycle (accordant to hot press procedure) was analysed (heating rate 2°C/min in dynamic segments). The presented data were averaged over two measurements.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 2 representative SEM images of the applied wool/rayon fabric are shown. The fibers are oriented randomly and fibre volume content is low in general. Hence, compaction characteristics must be addressed carefully during impregnation and processing. The rayon fibers exhibit a smooth fiber surface and a circular cross section. In contrast, the wool fibres show a rough, imbricated surface. In general the cross section of the wool fibres is larger than that of the rayon fibres.

Figure 2: SEM images of the investigated wool/rayon fabric.

Previous investigations showed that bubbles and spikes were formed during the second curing step (heating up from 90 to 120 °C and curing at 120 min at 120°C). Hence, in the following, the curing

characteristics of the resin as well as evaporation of volatiles during curing are discussed. In Fig. 3 degrees of conversion of the resin after different processing steps determined by DSC are compared. Both, pure resin and impregnated fibres are displayed. The graph in the left shows results from measurements in air, the graph in the right shows results from measurements in nitrogen. In general, atmosphere and fibres do not affect the reaction enthalpy of the resin. Values around 210 J/g were recorded. Hence, oxygen generally does not affect curing of the resin. However, oxygen may act as a reaction inhibitor during pre-curing at 90°C. Whereas degrees of conversion reach almost 60% in nitrogen atmosphere, they range around 35% in air atmosphere. Fibres decrease the degree of conversion in both atmospheres slightly. After the second curing step at 120°C degrees of conversion reach values around 97%. Fibres do not affect the degree of conversion there.

Figure 3: Degrees of conversion after different processing steps. Left: air atmosphere, right: nitrogen atmosphere.

In Fig. 4 the residual weights of resin (left) and fibre (right) after different processing steps determined by TGA are compared. Moreover the weight loss in a heating ramp from 25 to 200°C is shown.

Figure 4: Residual weight of resin (left) and fibre (right) determined by TGA after different processing steps.

In a single heating ramp the weight loss of the resin is about 3%. During the curing reaction applied for eco-leather production, the resin shows an even higher weight loss of around 5%. The highest weight loss occurs during heating from ambient to 90°C and during the second curing step at 120°C. This can be attributed to CO₂ generated by the tert-butyl peroxybenzoate initiator during reaction on the one hand. On the other hand residual volatiles within the resin evaporate. This may trigger the formation of volatile-induced voids and is correlating with previous investigations showing formation of bubbles and spikes during the second curing step.

However, in Fig. 5 micrographs showing the surface of eco-leather samples produced with 4.5 parts of resin (left) and with 6 parts of resin (right) are displayed. Both samples were fully impregnated. Bubble-shaped features are distributed randomly across the surface and not necessarily attached to the fibers. Hence, fibre type and surface structure do not affect occurrence and shape of features. Moreover, shape and quantity of features is not differing for the two samples. Thus, they are most-likely not attributable to volatiles evaporating from the resin. Otherwise, quantity should be larger for the sample produced with 6 parts of resin.

Figure 5: Micrographs of eco-leather surface samples produced with 4.5 (left) and 6 (right) weight parts of resin.

The weight loss of the fibres (Fig. 4 right) in a single heating ramp is 3.5%. During the curing reaction applied for eco-leather production, the fibres show a high weight loss of over 6%. The highest weight loss occurs during slow (2°C/min) heating from ambient temperature to 90°C. Afterwards the weight remains almost constant. The weight loss is attributable to evaporation of water/moisture. This can be deduced from Fig. 6 which depicts TGA and DSC heating curves of the fibres. The weight loss of the fibres excellently correlates with the endo-thermal water/moisture evaporation peak determined by DSC. However, moisture from the fibres is released prior to both applied curing steps. Hence, moisture is most-likely not causing volatile induced voids in eco-leather.

Figure 5: TGA and DSC heating curves of fibres recorded at 2 °C/min.

According to the generated results, spike and bubble shaped features in eco-leather are probably not caused by intrinsic material characteristics. More likely complex interactions between bio-based materials and processing parameters may result in unusual surface and interface phenomena, which affect performance characteristics of the new material.

5 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Within the present study especially intrinsic material effects on the formation of voids in eco-leather – a highly innovative natural fibre composite – were analysed. Parameter studies and comprehensive morphological and thermo-analytical investigations revealed that intrinsic material characteristics are most likely not the reason for voids (spike and bubble shaped features). However, there are complex interactions between resin and fibre, as resin is absorbed by the fibre during impregnation. Combined with the specific compaction behaviour of the investigated fibres, this complicates appropriate fabric impregnation and may hence trigger the formation of voids (mechanical entrapment). Future studies will address these aspects in detail by systematic parameter analysis in order to tailor breathability and other selective transport characteristics.

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